

D6.9 Final report on the contribution to standardization

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

Deliverable D6.9 “Final report on the contribution to standardization” is produced in the context of SunCOChem WP6, Task 6.3 “Standardisation activities”, in particular with regard to the subtask 6.3.2 “Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments”. This deliverable includes a summary of all standardization-related activities performed during the project, with a special focus on the contribution to new standards, performed since M24 to M54.

The transfer of SunCOChem results to standards being widely recognized by the industry and published by independent standardization organizations, external to the consortium, is a way to increase the impact of the project results beyond its duration. Additionally, the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardization committees.

Main standardization activities in the project have been the following:

1. Identification of existing standards and related standardization organizations and technical committees (reported in D6.2).
2. Elaboration of a strategy for the SunCOChem contribution to standardization.
3. Contacts with potentially interested standardization technical committees in CEN and ISO (reported in D6.5).
4. Analysis of the standardization potential of project outcomes and possible tracks, and selection of the most promising.
5. Standardization process for elaboration of a new standardization document in CEN.

The main outcome of this project activity has been the publication by the European Standards Organization CEN of [CWA 18147:2024](#) “*Testing and evaluating the performance of electrolyzers for reduction of CO₂ to CO*”, proposed and led by SunCOChem partners, based on the outcomes of the project.

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List of abbreviations

CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC CLC	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
CCMC	CEN-CENELEC Management Centre
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
EU	European Union
ERA	European Research Area
ISO	International Standards Organisation/International Standard published by ISO
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission/International Standard published by IEC
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization/Spanish national standard

1. SCOPE

This report describes a summary of all standardization-related activities performed during the project, with a special focus on the contribution to new standards, performed since M24 to M54.

D6.9 is built upon the conclusions of two previous documents:

1. D6.2 “Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards”, made available at M6, that includes the information on the existing and under development standards relevant for the project and the responsible standardization technical committees.
2. D6.5 “Initial report on the contribution to standardization”, available in M24, including the strategy of SunCOChem’s standardization activities and the description of the contacts held with interested standardization technical committees from CEN and ISO.

Additionally, a detailed description of the decisions taken regarding the contribution to new standards, the processes followed and the outcome obtained (CWA 18147:2024), is the main content of the report.

The objectives of these standardization activities in the project are to:

- Disseminate the results and objectives of SunCOChem using the network of the standardization community;
- Foster the market uptake of some SunCOChem results, making them more accessible to industry in Europe and worldwide, increasing this way their impact.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as a European National Standardisation Body, Member of CEN and ISO, has been the partner in the SunCOChem project to provide support regarding all the standardisation tasks included in this report.

2. PREVIOUS STANDARDIZATION ACTIVITIES IN THE PROJECT

2.1 Identification of standardization landscape

At the beginning of the project (M6), D6.2 “Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards” identified a set of standards related to SunCOChem fields of activity, for instance Photocatalysis, Solar energy, Nanotechnologies, Environment and CO₂ treatment, Chemistry, analysis and testing, etc. Moreover, the related technical committees were also identified, as a basis for the next activities.

2.2 Initial contribution to standardization

Initially, a strategy for the activities to be performed during the rest of the project was planned and included in D6.5 “Initial report on the contribution to standardization”. Figure 1 shows this plan.

Figure 1: Strategy for the SunCOChem contribution to standardization

Following this plan, a first contact with standardization committees was launched by e-mail, to raise awareness about SunCOChem among the different participating stakeholders and check the interest of the committees in the expected project outcomes and get any possible feedback.

A total of 9 committees were contacted, receiving positive interest feedback from 4 of them and general interest from 2 more. In a second step, invitations to present and discuss the project in committee meetings were received from some of them and 3 presentations were performed by SunCOChem partners in CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”, CEN/TC 352 “Nanotechnologies” and CEN/TC 467 “Climate change”. See D6.5 for details.

CEN/TC 386 is the most closely related (Photocatalysis), and has been involved in further project activities, as explained in chapter 3.

3. STANDARDIZATION PROCESS

3.1 Internal discussion and preparation

The main objective of the standardization activities in SunCOChem is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring project results and findings to standards that will have a wide recognition in the market.

The implication of all the partners is critical in this first stage, as the decisions to be taken will heavily depend on their exploitation strategies, their commercial and scientific interests and their willingness to be involved in standardization activities.

On 21 February 2022, a project-internal standardization session organized by UNE was held. The aim was to get a clear understanding on the objectives of the contribution to standardization and the standardization process to follow, and to identify the project results which can go through a standardization process.

Four topics related to the objectives and activities of SunCOChem, for which a contribution to standardization might be prepared, were identified:

- Evaluating/testing performance of photoelectron-catalysts for CO₂ reduction and water oxidation.
- Determination of targets characteristics for photocatalytic reactors/devices in order to progress in the development.
- Creation of a standard cell allowing a comparison of performance of different catalysts.
- Safety protocol for the construction of TPER.

A further analysis of the topics was coordinated among the SunCOChem partners, using a survey sent by UNE, to check the extent of confidential information needed as an input and availability of related SunCOChem deliverables linked with these topics.

According to this analysis, the selected topic was agreed initially as “Testing and evaluating the performance of a device for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO”. The leadership on this area is from partners Avantium and Politecnico di Torino. From the different standardization options available (see figure 1, last box), the CEN Workshop Agreement was selected as most adequate under different reasons:

- This is a kind of standard especially indicated for innovative topics coming from research and innovation projects.
- It is possible to develop in a short time (some months), in comparison with longer developing times in Technical Committees options (EN, TR, TS).
- Although CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis” is closely related to the scope to be standardized, they were not currently dealing with such topic.

On 27 March 2023, a second internal session on standardization was conducted to explain to the partners the concept of the CWA and to decide on additional details for the expected contents of the selected topic to be proposed. Annex A shows the contents of the session.

3.2 The CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)

A **CEN Workshop Agreement, CWA**, is a kind of standardization document, developed by a CEN Workshop, which reflects the agreement between identified individuals and organizations responsible for their contents, and which is published by CEN. It can further be the basis for a future European or international standard.

It is suitable for innovative markets where there is often a request for a reference document to be quickly developed as a first step to standardization, facilitating interoperability and compatibility, enhancing market uptake of innovative solutions and facilitating further incremental innovations in the market.

A **CEN Workshop** is a technical body with a short-term task specified in its project plan. All interested parties can voluntarily take part in the CEN Workshop. Moreover, there are different stages in which a draft CWA can be subjected to public commenting phases, even from non-participants in the CEN Workshop. The direct participation of interested parties, the possibility to list the participants and their organizations in the foreword and the quick development process, made the CWA particularly attractive for European research and innovation projects, which must deliver results within the limited duration of their project lifetimes.

Although a CWA is developed outside the normal CEN/CENELEC Technical Committees structure, it is important to ensure the coherence of all the different CEN/CENELEC documents in order to protect the reliability of European standardization. A CWA, therefore, shall not conflict with an existing European Standard and shall be withdrawn if a conflicting European Standard is published afterwards. However, a CWA can compete with another CWA, allowing this way different solutions to be tested and selected by the market.

Interest and collaboration from the related Technical Committees is encouraged as these documents, especially covering innovative and emerging topics, can be seeding their future work programmes or the creation of new standardization areas.

The CWA and the process of its elaboration is defined in [CEN/CENELEC Guide 29:2024](#).

NOTE: This clause 3.2 includes generic information about CWAs, and the same or similar text can be found in other deliverables written by UNE in different projects.

3.3 The CEN Workshop SunCOChem

After the decision of promoting a new CWA as the standardization outcome of the project, partner UNE started the preparation of the process, as a national Member of CEN. The following required roles were defined:

- Proposed Chair of the CEN Workshop: Bart van den Bosch (Avantium)
- Proposed Vice-chair of the CEN Workshop: Simelys Hernández (Politecnico di Torino)
- CEN Workshop Secretariat: UNE

The following steps were required to develop a CWA, according to CEN/CENELEC Guide 29:

1. Initiation stage

A CEN Workshop Proposal Form was prepared, according to the template provided by CEN. It was sent to CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) to start the process. The new

CEN Workshop, the project plan, the agenda for the kickoff meeting and the first draft of the CWA were announced in the CEN/CENELEC webpage (<https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2023/workshop/2023-06-16-suncochem/>) on 2023-06-16. There was a 30-days period for commenting and appointing experts up to the kickoff meeting.

Promotion of the announcement was done in the web and social media of SunCOChem, and direct invitations were sent to the most related technical committees: CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”, CEN/TC 352 “Nanotechnologies” and CEN/TC 467 “Climate change”.

The CEN Workshop proposal made emphasis on the fact that the conversion of CO₂ into chemicals, but also fuels, using energy derived from renewable energy sources, has the potential to reduce the use of fossil feedstocks. Although the Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) reaction is a relatively mature process to perform the CO₂ to CO conversion, it requires the input of hydrogen, which must be produced in a separate process. Electrochemical conversion of CO₂ to CO is an alternative process which could take place in a single conversion process, thereby reducing the number of unit operations and the costs. Such a process is currently not industrially applied and still in development phase. As there are many different technologies for electrochemical CO₂ conversion to CO, a standard for determining various process characteristics, or KPI’s, is required and will benefit the European industry.

2. CEN Workshop kickoff meeting

The CEN-CENELEC Workshop on “Testing and evaluating the performance of devices for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO” formally started its activity on 2023-07-20 with an online kick-off meeting. The list of attendees, most of them from SunCOChem partners, was the following:

- Maria Navarro (ES)
- Miriam Díaz de los Bernardos (ES)
- Bart van den Bosch (NL)
- Simelys Hernández (IT)
- Hilmar Guzmán Medina (IT)
- Federica Zammillo (IT)
- Juqin Zeng (IT)
- Freddy Liendo (IT)
- Angelica Chiodoni (IT)
- Daniele Sassone (IT)
- Pietro Guarato (BE)
- Samuel Lorenz (DE)
- Denis Koltsov (UK)
- Yu Zhang (BE)
- Steffen Jenkel (ES)

No comments were received before or during the meeting, so the proposed project plan was approved as it was.

The intended table of contents of the CWA was presented, and different drafters for the different chapters were allocated among the participants in the CEN Workshop.

See Annex B for the kick-off meeting agenda.

3. CWA drafting stage

A full-text draft was available in February 2024, and distributed to all CEN Workshop participants.

The second meeting of the CEN Workshop was scheduled on 19 April 2024, in Amsterdam, coinciding with the project General Assembly in M48. See Annex B for the agenda. A fruitful discussion was held, reaching agreements on different comments to the existing text. The most important ones were:

- To simplify the title of the CWA to: “Testing and evaluating the performance of 11lectrolyzers for reduction of CO₂ to CO”.
- Clarifying the production rate and energy efficiency parameters used.
- Improve the coherence of units.
- Review chapter 9 on Protocols for 11lectrolyzer performance.

An updated version according to these improvements was circulated in June 2024 and, after including some comments received, it was sent to CCMC for holding a public commenting period of 45 days, finishing on 22 August 2024. During this period, the draft CWA was made publicly available in the CEN-CENELEC webpage (<https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2024/workshop/2024-07-08-suncochem/>) and also sent to CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”, asking for any comment to the draft.

After a few received comments were adapted into the text, the final draft was approved by the CEN Workshop participants in September 2024, and submitted to CCMC for publication.

4. CWA publication

The CWA was finally published by CEN on 09-10-2024.

Its code is CWA 18147:2024 “Testing and evaluating the performance of 11lectrolyzers for reduction of CO₂ to CO”.

In order to allow for open access to the CWA, SunCOChem’s budget covered the cost established by CEN-CENELEC regulations for providing the published CWAs under public access. Therefore, the CWA can be downloaded free of charge from the CWA Download Area of CEN-CENELEC webpage:

https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/2024/cwa18147_2024.pdf

The scope of the CWA is the following:

“This document specifies procedures and protocols for testing and evaluating the performance of 11lectrolyzers for the reduction of CO₂ to CO. This is done by specifying test methods and key parameters for the determination of the performance with regard to:

- *production rate per electrode area (see clause 5),*
- *purity of the produced gas/product gas composition (see clause 6),*
- *stability of the reactor (see clause 7), and*
- *energy consumption (see clause 8).*

Additionally, protocols for the evaluation of 11lectrolyzer performance are specified (see clause 9).

This document does not specify requirements for the construction or the performance of electrolyzers for the reduction of CO₂ to CO.

It is limited to low-temperature technologies (< 80°C) and systems with water oxidation as the complementary reaction to CO₂ reduction.

This document is intended to be used by organisations and persons manufacturing or using such devices.”

Sister projects and related technical committees were informed about the publication and provided with the direct link to the CWA. Publication was also advertised through the project media and from UNE's ones.

4. CONCLUSIONS

With the elaboration and successful publication of a CEN Workshop Agreement, CWA 18147:2024, the main objective of the standardization task in SunCOChem is considered as fulfilled. Wide visibility has been given to the project as promoter of this document. Also, the new standard which has been made available, can be used by the industry players to help upscaling this technology. This way, part of the knowledge gathered and generated by the project has been transferred to industry and can revert into technical and economic benefits for Europe, following this way the recommendations of the [European Policy for Knowledge Valorisation](#) and the [Code of Practice on Standardisation in the ERA](#).

Additionally, the contact with different related standardization technical committees, composed by interested stakeholders from European and world-wide countries, has contributed to the dissemination of the project. Relevant information about SunCOChem was delivered to the selected standardization committees making the project being known through the internal communication channels of the European and international standardization system.

As a final advantage, thanks to this activity, SunCOChem partners and sister projects became more familiar with standardization, which is expected to be for them an advantage in their future European projects and innovation activities.

Annex A

2nd SunCOChem standardization session – Presentation slides

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SunCOChem
2nd Standardization Workshop
27 March 2023

Progress Compartido

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Goals of the meeting

1. Introduction CEN Workshop Agreement
2. Presentation of the results so far and discussion
3. Preparation of Workshop Proposal
4. Preparation of Draft Workshop Project Plan

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Introduction
CEN Workshop Agreement

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What is a CWA?

- a CEN WORKSHOP AGREEMENT (CWA) is a document agreed by the participants of a CEN Workshop (WS), that commonly is composed by H2020 project partners.
- a CWA normally includes guidelines, recommendations, best practices, test methods... and can be converted in a CEN standard in the future.

Examples: [CWA Download Area](#)

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Why to develop a CWA?

- As long as the innovative solutions have not reached a sufficient level of stability, a formal standard may be a less suitable solution considering the process in place as well as the obligations on the CEN/CENELEC national members to implement all European Standards.
- Once finalized and published, a CWA can be proposed for conversion into a European Standard to a corresponding Technical Committee (e.g., in CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis").
- The authors/workshop participants are mentioned (names and organisation) in the European Foreword
- Relatively short development time
- Very high influence of SunCoChem partners on the content of the CWA
- CWA will be publicly available (free to read and download) via the CEN/CENELEC homepage
- Published CWA to be used for dissemination and exploitation activities

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Development of a CWA (1)

INITIATION	DRAFTING	FINALISATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposal - Project plan - Self-assessment - Analysis of interest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kick-off meeting - Chair - Secretariat (UNE) • Drafting • Open commenting phase (recommended) • Final agreement and approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submission to CEN • Publication

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Development of a CWA (2)

Timeline of CWA development:

- Proposal form submission (-1 month)
- Project plan development
- Open comment period on draft prop. plan (-1 month)
- Kick-off meeting
- CWA development
- Open comment period on draft CWA (-1 month)
- CWA finalisation
- CWA publication

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Testing and evaluating the performance of a device for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO

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CWA Document structure

Foreword

1. Scope
2. Normative references
3. Terms and definitions
4. ((Performance characteristics of a device for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO))
5. Test methods (with the typical subclause structure: General – Principle – Apparatus – Test sample preparation – Procedure (incl. operating conditions) – Expression of results – Test report)
6. Evaluation procedure (or Conclusion)

Annex(es)
Bibliography

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Scope

"Testing and evaluating the performance of a device for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO"

"This document specifies protocols for the performance evaluation of a device for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO. This is done by specifying test methods for the determination of the performance with regard to production rate per electrode area, purity of the produced gas/product gas composition, stability of the reactor and energy consumption."

(We don't want to standardize specific constructive solutions but instead the way how the performance of a Device can be measured and evaluated. The construction/the design of a Device is considered as a black box.)

- Something missing?
- Something to be added?
- Further clarifications needed?
- Exclusions?

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Terms and definitions

- Pure Appl. Chem., Vol. 83, No. 4, pp. 931–1014, 2011. Glossary of terms used in photocatalysis and radiation catalysis (IUPAC Recommendations2011) (<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1351/PAC-REC-09-09-36/html?lang=en>)
- EN 16981:2021, Photocatalysis - Glossary of terms
- ISO 8044:2020, Corrosion of metals and alloys — Vocabulary

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Performance characteristics

- a) production rate per electrode area
- b) purity of the produced gas/product gas composition
- c) stability of the reactor
- d) energy consumption.

Something to add?

Any contribution from SunCOChem deliverables?

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Test methods

The CWA will contain test methods for the determination of the performance with regard to

- production rate per electrode area
- purity of the produced gas/product gas composition
- stability of the reactor
- energy consumption

Standardized test methods to be referred to?
→ ISO/TC 158 "Analysis of gases"
→ ISO/TC 201 "Surface chemical analysis"

Any contribution from SunCOChem deliverables?

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Evaluation procedure

What has to be done here?

Any contribution from SunCOChem deliverables?

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Preparation of the proposal for a CEN Workshop

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Preparation of the Draft CEN Workshop project plan

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Annex B

CEN/WS SunCOChem – Kickoff and 2nd meetings agendas

2023-06-08

Draft Agenda for the kick-off meeting of CEN/WS "Testing and evaluating the performance of devices for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO (SUNCOCHEM project)"

Date: 20 July 2023

Time: 9:00-13:00

Venue: virtual via Webconference (Zoom)

Agenda	Timing
1. Opening of the meeting	9:00
2. Roll call of participants	9:05
3. Adoption of the agenda	9:20
4. Introduction on CEN and on the Workshop concept	9:25
5. General presentation of the Workshop (Idea, motivation and expected benefit of the new standard)	9:35
6. Election and appointment of Workshop Chair and Vice-Chair Confirmation of the Secretariat	10:00
7. Project Plan	10:10
a) Discussion and review of comments received on the Draft project plan	
b) Adoption of the Project Plan (by consensus)	
Break	10:45
8. Organization of the technical work	11:00
a) Discussion of first draft of CWA	
b) Review of available source material	
c) Creation of work packages and responsible working groups	
d) Coordination of project milestones	

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|---|-------|
| 9. Any other business | 12:15 |
| 10. Next meeting, future actions and their assignment | 12:30 |
| 11. Closure of the meeting | 13:00 |

|

**Draft Agenda for the 2nd meeting of
CEN/WS SUNCOCHEM
"Testing and evaluating the performance of devices for
electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to CO"**

*Date: 19 April 2024
Time: 11:00-13:00 (CEST)*

Venue: virtual via TEAMS [Click here to join the meeting](#)

Agenda	Timing
1. Opening of the meeting	11:00
2. Roll call of participants	11:05
3. Discussion of draft CWA v1.2	11:15
4. Next actions and their assignment	12:15
5. Any other business	12:40
6. Next meeting, future actions and their assignment	12:45
7. Closure of the meeting	13:00